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EXPERIENCE OF FOREIGN COUNTRIES IN RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN MANAGER AND EMPLOYEE

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Annotation. In this article, it is proposed to implement certain elements of relations between managers and employees by studying the experience of foreign countries.

Keywords: hierarchy, leader, motivation, mediation, consensus, employee, stress, team, conflict, listening.

Today, in all companies, manufacturing industries, modern professions and almost every field, improving the relationship between managers and employees, preventing and eliminating problems that may arise and still exist between them - increasing work efficiency in enterprises and labor is one of the main factors to improve conditions.

In order to develop Uzbek companies like world-class companies, it is necessary to study the experience of foreign countries and put it into practice.

Manager-employee relationships in Japan are characterized by a strong emphasis on hierarchy, respect, and loyalty. Managers must lead and make decisions. And the employees must follow the instructions and show their commitment to their work. Open communication between managers and employees has always been encouraged in Japan. Building trust and maintaining harmonious relationships are key aspects of Japanese management culture.

Handling conflicts between managers and employees in Japan requires a delicate approach. This can be approached as follows:

1. Communication: Encourage open and respectful communication between the manager and the employee involved in the conflict. As we mentioned above, open communication between the leader and the employee, the ability of the employee to express his thoughts, prevents problems between the leader and the employee. This method has always been considered one of the best in Japan.

2. Mediation: A neutral third party, such as a human resources representative or senior manager, should be involved to mediate the conflict. Nowadays, HR managers work in companies in all developed countries. They are involved not only in the regulation of relations between employees, but also in

management and employee relations. Their task will be to facilitate a constructive dialogue and find a mutually acceptable solution.

3. Respect for hierarchy: Japanese organizations recognize and respect the hierarchical structure. That is, the employees obey the decisions of the above leaders. A key factor in this structure is that managers listen to the opinions and concerns of their subordinates, and that employees express their views respectfully.

4. Seek consensus: encourage both parties to find common ground and work toward a solution that benefits all involved. The main focus should be on reaching a compromise that is consistent with the overall goals of the organization.

5. Building Relationships: Encourage teamwork and opportunities for managers and employees to interact outside of work-related tasks. This helps to build better understanding and trust between the two parties.

6. Continuous Improvement: Foster a culture of continuous improvement that welcomes and acts on feedback. Regularly review and revise policies and procedures to address any major issues that may lead to conflicts.

Remember that it takes time and patience to resolve conflicts. It is important to approach these situations with empathy and a willingness to find a mutually beneficial solution.

Manager-employee relationships in America are generally characterized by a more egalitarian and informal approach compared to some other cultures.

In America, more emphasis is often placed on open and direct communication between managers and employees. Both parties are encouraged to express their opinions, concerns and ideas freely. Cooperation and teamwork are highly valued in American workplaces. Managers often ask employees for their opinions and encourage their active participation in decision-making processes.

Of course, incentives also play an important role in the relationship between managers and employees in America. Managers provide regular feedback, set performance goals, and recognize achievements to motivate and guide employees.

American culture places great emphasis on individualism, and this is reflected in the relationship between managers and employees. Employees are encouraged to take ownership of their work and contribute their unique skills and ideas. The creativity of employees is duly rewarded. That is, promotion,

financial rewards or similar incentives are determined. These play an important role in motivating employees.

Work-life balance is increasingly important in American workplaces. Managers often support employees' personal lives and strive to create a flexible and comfortable work environment. Manager-employee relations in America are also influenced by various legal frameworks such as labor laws and regulations. These laws protect the rights of employees and provide guidelines for fair treatment and non-discrimination. It is important to note that workplace dynamics can vary across industries, organizations and regions of America. However, the overall trend is towards fostering open communication, collaboration and a positive work environment.

In America, conflict resolution between managers and employees can be done through the following steps:

1. Encourage open communication: Create a culture that promotes open and honest communication between managers and employees. This helps both parties express their concerns, perspectives and ideas.

2. Active listening: Managers should actively listen to employees to understand their grievances and concerns. It helps build trust and empathy and helps resolve conflicts better.

3. Mediation: If a conflict persists, a neutral third party, such as an HR representative or a mediator, is brought in to facilitate productive dialogue and find a mutually acceptable solution.

4. Setting clear expectations: Make sure managers and employees have a clear understanding of their roles, responsibilities and expectations. That is, the fact that everyone in the company knows their duties will cause fewer conflicts. This helps to avoid conflicts arising from misunderstandings.

5. Provide training and development opportunities: offer training programs focused on conflict resolution, effective communication and leadership skills. Conflicts arise less with employees who know their job well and have a sufficient level of communication. It helps managers and employees develop the necessary skills to resolve conflicts constructively.

6. Create a positive work environment: Create an inclusive work environment where employees feel valued and respected. Teamwork, collaboration, and recognition of accomplishments help reduce conflict.

As a matter of fact, in all developed countries, special attention is paid to manager-employee relations. As we have seen above, we can understand that in both Japan and America, listening to employees, encouraging them, and helping

them solve their problems are among the main and common solutions. It is important to remember that each conflict is unique and it is important to evaluate each situation individually to find the best solution.

It should be noted that it is no secret that one of the sensitive issues in Uzbek companies is that misunderstandings between managers and employees cause major conflicts. The solution is simple, we need to organize work through interaction based on the employee's needs. Training and empowering human resources (HRM) managers is one of the biggest challenges facing modern companies today. When studying the above experiences, it is possible to draw up a plan to improve the relationship between employees by developing a special offer and an individual psychological approach to each employee.

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